

Enhancing Creative Distant Learning in higher Education Institutions in a digital society

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Annotation Distance learning courses in this form introduce students to the essence of innovations in the field of law, introduce the latest achievements in the field, improve professional skills, develop skills to overcome systemic shortcomings, and constantly improve the level of training during their careers, timely theoretical and practical can serve to ensure the effectiveness of increasing professional competence through the application of knowledge, skills and competencies in practice.

Keywords: distance learning, a new stage of development, organization of courses, educational process, training, specialists, universities

"New Uzbekistan" on a global scale testifies to the recognition that in recent years we have entered a completely new stage of development - a stage of huge transformations and achievements.

In the modern information age and the pandemic, it is important to create a system of distance learning in higher education institutions.

Many countries use modern ICT-based distance learning (MT) to train quality personnel in the education system. The experience of the education system shows that opportunities are expanding to radically improve the quality of personnel through the use of the Internet and ICT in the learning process as a means of acquiring, storing, transferring new knowledge and practical decision-making.

The pace of development of the territory, the structure of the economy determine which highly qualified specialists are needed in the region, as well as the content of the requirements for graduates of educational institutions. In turn, the socio-

economic situation in the region has a significant impact on the level and dynamics of youth migration. Prosperous regions attract a large flow of young people from other regions, which creates competition for local specialists. The presence of workers with different skill levels in the labor market increases the expectations and requirements of employers, which also changes the perception of the quality of the activities of local universities.

The prospects for the development of partnerships between higher education and regional authorities are associated with the strengthening of social and political support for universities, the implementation of joint projects, and increase in the volume of services provided by higher education institutions

What is Distance Learning?

Distance education is a process of remote and interactive communication between students and teachers with the introduction of the goal, content, methods, means of study and Internet technologies of the educational process.

Distance education is a configuration learning, based on a comprehensive distance learning of all disciplines in the system of training specialists of a particular profile, and not on symbolically established criteria for the place and time of the learning process within the framework of the complex. In order to fully and correctly understand the essence of this definition, it is necessary to translate it with the definition of distance learning mentioned above.

Distance learning is considered a more necessary and increasingly well-known form of modern education. Distance learning is a new modern form of education that develops students' ability to think independently, assess the situation, manage their rights and bear obligations, take meaningful actions, and draw conclusions. Teaches self-knowledge, research, study of thinking.

The advantage of distance learning is that each student can study at a convenient time, place, environment. In this regard, it is this system that is gaining popularity in the world today during the concept of the Third Renaissance and New Uzbekistan. On the positive side of distance education, today many universities and large enterprises around the world use this method to improve the skills of specialists, saving millions of dollars a year.

There are also organizational and financial and economic advantages of distance learning, such as the fact that classrooms, boards, desks and other learning technologies are not required for learning. Financial costs are mainly spent on the

development of educational materials and Internet traffic. Naturally, costs are reduced. The clearer and more detailed the learning materials are, the more useful they will be for the student.

How important is distance education in student learning?

This is an online training between a teacher and students of higher educational institutions. Such lectures, seminars, practical classes will require, first of all, communication, materials for distance education, electronic and regular textbooks, educational and methodological complexes, audio and video textbooks, online lessons (website), electronic libraries, tests, multimedia electronic textbooks and, of course, a computer connected to the Internet.

With such training, the student does not have to go to the university every day. At the same time, students living in other cities, students with disabilities can study through this system.

Literature:

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages". Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 2, Article 25;
2. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "On measures to raise to a qualitatively new level of activities to popularize the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan." National Database of Legislation, 20.05.2021, No. 07/21/5117/0472)
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, No. 2, Article 25; National Database of Legislation, 05.07.2019, No. 06/19/5759/3385, 10.09.2021, No. 06/21/6311/086
4. <https://studenty-distansionno-obuchavshiyesya-v-blijnem-zarubejye-jdut-prikaza-dlya-prodoljyeniya-uchyoby-v-uzbekistane /2020/07/03/>
5. Vakhobova M.A. Structural reforms in Uzbekistan. Supporting future-oriented learning and teaching. Republican Scientific and Practical Center for the Development of Innovative Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages “ Priority directions for the use of technologies for teaching different system languages
6. Khakimov N.H. The country's development strategy. Civil society. Latvia, Lambert. 2021. Page109.

7. Ibragimov I.M. Information technologies and means of distance learning: Proc. manual for students of higher educational institutions / Ed. A. N. Kovshova. M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2005.
8. Vakhobova M.A. Innovations in education as a necessary condition for the development of creativity of university students. Epra International journal of multidisciplinary research
9. Polat E. S., Bukharkina M. Yu., Moiseeva M. V. Theory and practice of distance learning: Proc. manual for students of higher pedagogical educational institutions / Ed. E. S. Polat. M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2004.
10. Khakimov N.H. Zulfikarov Sh.Kh., Kadirov N.N. Uzbekistan in the conditions of a new stage of development. Monograph. Tashkent, Iktisodiet, 2022. Page 223. (in Uzbek)